

connective tissue growth factor / cellular communication network factor 2 (CTGF / CCN2) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : CTGF, is a matricellular protein of the CCN family of extracellular matrix-associated heparin-binding proteins. It has been implicated in systemic sclerosis, wound healing, glioblastoma, mesenchymal tumors, renal fibrosis, fibroproliferative lung disease, inflammatory bowel disease, desmoplastic malignant melanoma, biliary atresia, pancreatic cancer, fibrosing hepatopathy, skeletal growth, diabetes, sporadic and familial amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, fetal growth restriction and cervical cancer, to name a few. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of CTGF, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed

*ML dicoveries of CTGF synergy in Meningiomas

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by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: CTGF, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp

et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angioma-tous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Wurttemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. connective tissue growth factor (CTGF)

Bradham et al. [13] purified platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF)-related activity from human umbilical vein endothelial (HUVE) cell-conditioned media. HUVE cells express the genes for the A and B chains of PDGF and secrete PDGF-related factors into culture media. They cloned and sequenced a cDNA with an open reading frame encoding a 38-kD cysteine-rich secreted protein which they showed to be the major PDGF-related mitogen secreted by human vascular endothelial cells. This protein had a 45% overall homology to the translation product of the v-src-induced CEF-10 mRNA

from chick embryo fibroblasts, which they termed as connective tissue growth factor (CTGF).

Martinerie et al. [14] identified and mapped the human locus (novH) corresponding to the nov protooncogene overexpressed in avian nephroblastoma, on chromosome 8q24.1. Further, they mapped another locus sharing homology with novH and corresponding to CTGF gene on chromosome 6q23.1.

Igarashi et al. [15] found high levels of CTGF mRNA and protein being produced by human foreskin fibroblasts. Because of the high level selective induction of CTGF by TGF- β , they believed that CTGF was produced by TGF- β -treated human skin fibroblasts. Further, they observed that Cycloheximide did not block the large TGF- β stimulation of CTGF gene expression, thus indicating that it was directly regulated by TGF- β .

1.3. Roles of CTGF in different disease

Igarashi et al. [16] studied the distribution of CTGF gene expression in tissue sections from patients with **systemic sclerosis** (SSc) using digoxigenin-labeled in situ hybridization. They observed strong CTGF mRNA signals in the fibroblasts in sclerotic lesions, especially in the deep dermis, of the skin specimens from patients with SSc, while no expression in the skin from normal controls was observed. Their findings indicated a correlation between CTGF gene expression and skin sclerosis and supported the hypothesis that TGF- β played an role in the pathogenesis of SSc.

Igarashi et al. [16] studied an in vitro model of **wound healing** to study cell migration that was independent of proliferation during renal regeneration after acute tubular necrosis. For this, they subjected monolayer cultures of high-density, quiescent renal epithelial cells of the BSC-1 line to scrape wounding. They found that after wounding the monolayer, there was maximal induction of the immediate-early genes EGR-1, c-FOS, NAK-1, and GRO at 1 hour, followed by peak induction of CTGF and c-myc at 4 hours. Further, message levels of urokinase-type plasminogen activator (u-PA) and its inhibitor (PAI-1) and heat shock protein (HSP)-70 were markedly raised 4-8 hours after wounding. Differential expression of genes was a function of cell location relative to the wound and CTGF was induced in each of these populations suggesting that cell-to-cell communication may regulate gene expression after wounding.

Xin et al. [17] investigated expression of two structurally related genes, nephroblastoma overexpressed gene (novH) and CTGF, in human derived **glioblastoma** cell lines. Also, they investigated whether the same transcription factors regulate CTGF and novH expression. They found that CTGF and novH mRNA levels differed in the glioma cell lines, but they were not co-expressed in all cell lines. They also observed that the CTGF promoter region was highly conserved compared with the corresponding region in the mouse (FISP12) and exhibited in vitro transcriptional activity.

Igarashi et al. [18] investigated the CTGF gene and CD34 antigen expression in **mesenchymal tumors**. They observed that CTGF mRNA was expressed in fibroblasts of all nine dermatofibromas examined, but five of seven dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans (DFSP) or two cases of malignant fibrous histiocytoma were found to be -ive for its expression. Further, in vascular tumors, they observed that CTGF mRNA was expressed in pyogenic granuloma but not in angiosarcoma. In addition, the endothelial

cells in angioliipoma and angioleiomyoma, but not in venous lake, expressed CTGF mRNA. Thus, their findings indicated that benign fibroblasts and/or vascular endothelial cells had the capability to express CTGF mRNA when activated, but these cells lost this ability when they achieved malignant potency.

Ito et al. [19] investigated CTGF mRNA expression in 65 human renal biopsy specimens of various renal diseases by in situ hybridization. They observed that CTGF mRNA was mainly expressed in visceral epithelial cells, parietal epithelial cells, and some interstitial cells, in control human kidney. Further, CTGF was strongly up-regulated in the extracapillary and severe mesangial proliferative lesions of crescentic glomerulonephritis, IgA nephropathy, focal and segmental glomerulosclerosis and diabetic nephropathy. Also, they observed an increase in the number of cells expressing CTGF mRNA at sites of chronic tubulointerstitial damage, which correlated with the degree of damage. In the tubulointerstitial area the majority of the CTGF mRNA positive cells coexpressed α -smooth muscle actin, and were negative for macrophage markers. Thus they concluded that CTGF might play a role in **renal fibrosis**.

The CTGF gene promoter contains a TGF- β 1 response element. Since TGF- β 1 expression was upregulated in several models of **fibroproliferative lung disease**, Lasky et al. [20] asked whether CTGF was also upregulated in a murine lung fibrosis model and whether CTGF could mediate some of the fibrogenic effects associated with TGF- β 1. They observed a greater than 2-fold increase in CTGF expression in both human and murine lung fibroblasts 2, 4, and 24 h after the addition of TGF- β 1 in vitro. Further, they observed that CTGF mRNA expression was upregulated in the sensitive, but not in the resistant, mouse strain after administration of bleomycin (lung fibrogenic agent). Their data showed that CTGF was expressed in lung fibroblasts and might play a role in the pathogenesis of lung fibrosis. **Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD)** is a multifactorial disorder which is characterized by massive damage of the epithelium and the underlying mesenchyme of the intestine. Dammeier et al. [21] investigated the possible role of CTGF in IBD, as it has an important role on fibroblast proliferation and connective tissue deposition. They showed an increased expression of CTGF mRNA in surgical specimens of patients suffering from two forms of IBD, Crohn's disease and ulcerative colitis. Their data pointed to a prominent role of CTGF in the repair of mucosal injury in IBD and in the aberrant deposition of extracellular matrix, that led to fibrosis and stenosis, one major complication in IBD, especially in Crohn's disease.

Desmoplastic malignant melanoma (DMM) consists of amelanotic spindle-shaped melanoma cells and is accompanied by desmoplasia with fibrous stromata. Among the several fibrogenic cytokines and cytokine receptors in DMM, Kubo et al. [22] investigated the role of bFGF, CTGF, PDGF and PDGF receptors. They found that PDGF- β receptor, bFGF and CTGF were intensely expressed in the DMM specimens in comparison with the amelanotic malignant melanoma (AMM) specimens. They hypothesize that the reaction of PDGF-B ligand and CTGF to PDGF- β receptor, in addition to the expression of bFGF, might contribute to the desmoplasia in DMM.

Tamatani et al. [23] generated murine monoclonal antibodies against CTGF and confirmed that CTGF was specifically induced in human fibroblasts by TGF- β but not by PDGF, FGF, IGF-I, or EGF. They further found that the serum levels of CTGF were significantly correlated with the progression of hepatic fibrosis in **biliary atresia**.

Wenger et al. [24] isolated hCTGF as an immediate early target gene of EGF/TGF α

in human **pancreatic cancer** cells. They found CTGF transcripts in 13/15 pancreatic cancer cell lines incubated with 10% serum. In 3/7 pancreatic cancer cell lines EGF/TGF α was found to induce a significant rise of CTGF transcript levels peaking 1-2 h after the start of treatment. Further, TGF β increased CTGF transcript levels in 2/7 pancreatic cancer cell lines after 4 h of treatment and this elevation was sustained after 24 h. Also, 15/19 human pancreatic cancer tissues were shown to overexpress high levels of CTGF transcripts.

Abou-Shady et al. [25] investigated the role of CTGF **fibrosing hepatopathy**. They found a strong expression of CTGF mRNA in fibroblasts and myofibroblast-like cells present in fibrous septa surrounding the cirrhotic nodules, in stellate cells, in endothelial cells and in mesenchymal cells around ductular proliferations, and in ductular epithelial cells. They concluded that overexpression of CTGF in liver cirrhosis, especially in fibroblasts/myofibroblasts and stellate cells, suggested that it might play an important role in hepatic fibrosis.

In a review, Takigawa et al. [26] conclude that although the most important physiological role of CTGF/Hcs24 is ecogenin action, these factors also play important roles in **skeletal growth** and modeling/remodeling via its direct action on osteoblasts under both physiological and pathological conditions.

Previously it was shown that glomerular expression of the pro-sclerotic cytokine CCN2 (CTGF) is greatly up-regulated early in experimental and in human **diabetes** and mesangial cell exposure to CTGF increases its production of extracellular matrix (ECM) molecules responsible for glomerulosclerosis. As an early marker, Riser et al. [27] therefore investigated the presence of CTGF in urine and the relationship to diabetes and/or renal disease in an experimental model of diabetes and in a limited patient population. Their findings supported the hypothesis that CTGF was up-regulated early in the evolution of glomerulosclerosis, including that of diabetes. We contended that urinary CTGF may both stage nephropathy and predict those patients who are destined for progressive glomerulosclerosis and end-stage renal disease (ESRD).

Spliet et al. [28] investigated the expression of CTGF protein in the spinal cord of control and both **sporadic and familial amyotrophic lateral sclerosis** (sALS and fALS) patients. Western blot analysis showed a consistent increase in CTGF expression in six sALS patients compared with controls. Their data indicated a role for CTGF in the complex reactive process that was associated with the progression of ALS spinal cord damage. Further, the up-regulation in reactive astrocytes supported a role for CTGF in the molecular mechanisms underlying astrogliosis.

Fetal growth restriction (FGR) is a common complication of pregnancy, and insufficient syncytialization in the placenta might play an important role in the pathogenesis of FGR. Liu et al. [29] demonstrated that the level of syncytialization was decreased in FGR patient placentas, while the expression of CTGF was significantly upregulated. They found that CTGF inhibited trophoblast fusion via regulating cell cycle progress of BeWo cells.

In **cervical cancer** tissues, Ma et al. [30] WDR5 was significantly upregulated. Further, they observed that WDR5 interacted with YAP1, enhancing CTGF expression through histone methylation. In vivo, the oncogenic function of WDR5 was contingent upon the YAP1-CTGF signaling axis.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have

been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [31] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [32] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [32].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [33]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [34], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank}

Joachims [31] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM^{Rank}_{classify}$ Joachims [31]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [35], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine

ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. CTGF related synergies

Note - CTGF was found to be upregulated in Type B. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and FDR ≤ 0.001 , in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 392 2^{nd} order combinations of CTGF were recorded.

3.1.1. CTGF - individual genes

The following genes in combination with CTGF showed high rankings - prominin 1 (PROM1), flavin containing dimethylaniline monooxygenase 1 (FMO1), insulin like growth factor 1 (IGF1), elastin (ELN), solute carrier family 12 member 1 (SLC12A1), fibulin 1 (FBLN1), ADCYAP receptor type I (ADCYAP1R1), tripartite motif containing 9 (TRIM9), sushi repeat containing protein X-linked (SRPX), solute carrier family 17 member 7 (SLC17A7), AE binding protein 1 (AEBP1), bone marrow stromal cell antigen 1 (BST1), ST8 alpha-N-acetyl-neuraminide alpha-2,8-sialyltransferase 1 (ST8SIA1), natriuretic peptide receptor 3 (NPR3), chromosome 1 open reading frame 198 (C1orf198), PHD finger protein 19 (PHF19), plexin domain containing 2 (PLXDC2), PDZ and LIM domain 2 (PDLIM2), cysteine rich secretory protein LCCL domain containing 1 (CRISPLD1), C-C motif chemokine receptor 2 (CCR2), PHD finger protein 24 (PHF24), plasminogen activator, urokinase (PLAU), basic helix-loop-helix family member e41 (BHLHE41), solute carrier family 12 member 5 (SLC12A5), transmembrane protein 35A (TMEM35A), FCH and mu domain containing endocytic adaptor 1 (FCHO1), peroxidase (PXD), leukocyte immunoglobulin like receptor B2 (LILRB2), complement C1q like 1 (C1QL1), solute carrier family 6 member 11 (SLC6A11), myosin heavy chain 10 (MYH10), contactin 6 (CNTN6), protein tyrosine phosphatase non-receptor type 22 (PTPN22), formin homology 2 domain containing 3 (FHOD3), Fas apoptotic inhibitory molecule 2 (FAIM2), leucine rich repeats and calponin homology domain containing 1 (LRCH1), lymphocyte cytosolic protein 1 (LCP1), alpha kinase 3 (ALPK3), ectonucleotide pyrophosphatase/phosphodiesterase 2 (ENPP2), interleukin 11 receptor subunit alpha (IL11RA), phospholipase C beta 2 (PLCB2), elastin microfibril interfacer 1 (EMILIN1), Fraser extracellular matrix complex subunit 1 (FRAS1), cerebellin 3 precursor (CBLN3), fibulin 5 (FBLN5), milk fat globule

EGF and factor V/VIII domain containing (MFGE8), insulin like growth factor binding protein 4 (IGFBP4), chromosome 1 open reading frame 162 (C1orf162), RNA binding motif single stranded interacting protein 3 (RBMS3), oxysterol binding protein like 10 (OSBPL10), family with sequence similarity 198 member A (FAM198A), CTD small phosphatase like (CTDSPL), myosin heavy chain 15 (MYH15), family with sequence similarity 105 member A (FAM105A), phosphoinositide-3-kinase regulatory subunit 1 (PIK3R1), spermatogenesis associated 9 (SPATA9), LanC like family member 3 (LANCL3), carbohydrate sulfotransferase 7 (CHST7), ADAM metallopeptidase domain 12 (ADAM12), fasciculation and elongation protein zeta 1 (FEZ1), mohawk homeobox (MKX), AT-rich interaction domain 5B (ARID5B), serine protease 23 (PRSS23), cysteine rich transmembrane BMP regulator 1 (CRIM1), enkurin, TRPC channel interacting protein (ENKUR), ADAM metallopeptidase with thrombospondin type 1 motif 12 (ADAMTS12), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily E regulatory subunit 4 (KCNE4), dimethylarginine dimethylaminohydrolase 1 (DDAH1), roundabout guidance receptor 3 (ROBO3), chromosome 10 open reading frame 90 (C10orf90), matrix metallopeptidase 16 (MMP16), tetraspanin 7 (TSPAN7), sushi domain containing 3 (SUSD3), myosin IE (MYO1E), SLAM family member 8 (SLAMF8), RUNX family transcription factor 1 (RUNX1), meiosis 1 associated protein (M1AP), trichohyalin (TCHH), coiled-coil-helix-coiled-coil-helix domain containing 6 (CHCHD6), sialic acid binding Ig like lectin 11 (SIGLEC11), sialic acid binding Ig like lectin 16 (gene/pseudogene) (SIGLEC16), LDL receptor related protein 5 (LRP5), ELAV like RNA binding protein 4 (ELAVL4), matrix remodeling associated 8 (MXRA8), NLR family pyrin domain containing 3 (NLRP3), coiled-coil domain containing 74A (CCDC74A), NK6 homeobox 1 (NKX6-1), EBF transcription factor 1 (EBF1), transmembrane protein 200A (TMEM200A), collagen type I alpha 2 chain (COL1A2), Htra serine peptidase 1 (HTRA1), microfibril associated protein 4 (MFAP4), trans-golgi network vesicle protein 23 homolog A (TVP23A), lactate dehydrogenase D (LDHD), proline rich transmembrane protein 2 (PRRT2), cytochrome P450 family 2 subfamily S member 1 (CYP2S1), 5'-nucleotidase domain containing 2 (NT5DC2), filamin A interacting protein 1 like (FILIP1L), RAB31, member RAS oncogene family (RAB31), nephronectin (NPNT), atonal bHLH transcription factor 8 (ATOH8), vesicle associated membrane protein 5 (VAMP5), armadillo repeat containing 4 (ARMC4), carnitine palmitoyltransferase 1C (CPT1C), coiled-coil domain containing 126 (CCDC126), G protein-coupled receptor 183 (GPR183), integrin subunit alpha M (ITGAM), G protein-coupled receptor 27 (GPR27), mono-ADP ribosylhydrolase 2 (MACROD2), interleukin 17D (IL17D), sushi domain containing 5 (SUSD5), heart development protein with EGF like domains 1 (HEG1), CD248 molecule (CD248), yippee like 2 (YPEL2), family with sequence similarity 131 member A (FAM131A), MEF2 activating motif and SAP domain containing transcriptional regulator (MAMSTR), frizzled class receptor 8 (FZD8), myozenin 1 (MYOZ1), phosphodiesterase 4D interacting protein (PDE4DIP), cysteine and serine rich nuclear protein 3 (CSRNP3), class II major histocompatibility complex transactivator (CIITA), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily E regulatory subunit 1 (KCNE1), NME/NM23 nucleoside diphosphate kinase 1 (NME1), PLAG1 zinc finger (PLAG1), exostosin glycosyltransferase 1 (EXT1), family with sequence similarity 43 member B (FAM43B), adrenoceptor alpha 2C (ADRA2C), colony stimulating factor 1 (CSF1), cytochrome P450 family 4

subfamily Z member 1 (CYP4Z1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily X member 1 (CYP4X1), reticulon 4 receptor like 2 (RTN4RL2), A-kinase anchoring protein 19 (C2orf88 / AKAP19), kelch repeat and BTB domain containing 12 (KBTBD12), nuclear GTPase, germinal center associated (NUGGC), serine/threonine kinase 31 (STK31), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 3(DACT3), adenosine deaminase RNA specific B1 (ADARB1), sialophorin (SPN), chromosome 2 open reading frame 27A (C2orf27A / LINC03124), C-type lectin domain containing 9A (CLEC9A), metallothionein 1F (MT1F), integrin subunit beta like 1 (ITGBL1), delta like canonical Notch ligand 1 (DLL1), dual specificity phosphatase and pro isomerase domain containing 1 (DUSP27), RNA, U6 small nuclear 529, pseudogene (RNU6-529P), family with sequence similarity 155 member A (FAM155A), transmembrane protein 240 (TMEM240), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 937 (LINC00937), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 1907 (LINC01907) and zinc finger protein 883 (ZINC883).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of CTGF with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t CTGF with CTGF – > PROM1 / FMO1 / IGF1 / ELN / SLC12A1 / FBLN1 / ADCYAP1R1 / TRIM9 / SRPX / SLC17A7 / AEBP1 / BST1 / ST8SIA1 / NPR3 / C1orf198 / PHF19 / PLXDC2 / PDLIM2 / CRISPLD1 / CCR2 / PHF24 / PLAU / BHLHE41 / SLC12A5 / TMEM35A / FCHO1 / PXDN / LILRB2 / C1QL1 / SLC6A11 / MYH10 / CNTN6 / PTPN22 / FHOD3 / FAIM2 / LRCH1 / LCP1 / ALPK3 / ENPP2 / IL11RA / PLCB2 / EMILIN1 / FRAS1 / CBLN3 / FBLN5 / MFGE8 / IGFBP4 / C1orf162 / RBMS3 / OSBPL10 / FAM198A / CTD-SPL / MYH15 / FAM105A / PIK3R1 / SPATA9 / LANCL3 / CHST7 / ADAM12 / FEZ1 / MKX / ARID5B / PRSS23 / CRIM1 / ENKUR / ADAMTS12 / KCNE4 / DDAH1 / ROBO3 / C10orf90 / MMP16 / TSPAN7 / SUSD3 / MYO1E / SLAMF8 / RUNX1 / M1AP / TCHH / CHCHD6 / SIGLEC11 / SIGLEC16 / LRP5 / ELAVL4 / MXRA8 / NLRP3 / CCDC74A / NKX6-1 / EBF1 / TMEM200A / COL1A2 / HTRA1 / MFAP4 / TVP23A / LDHD / PRRT2 / CYP2S1 / NT5DC2 / FILIP1L / RAB31 / NPNT / ATOH8 / VAMP5 / ARMC4 / CPT1C / CCDC126 / GPR183 / ITGAM / GPR27 / MACROD2 / IL17D / SUSD5 / HEG1 / CD248 / YPEL2 / FAM131A / MAMSTR / FZD8 / MYOZ1 / PDE4DIP / CSRNP3 / CIITA / KCNE1 / NME1 / PLAG1 / EXT1 / FAM43B / ADRA2C / CSF1 / CYP4Z1 / CYP4X1 / RTN4RL2 / C2orf88 / KBTBD12 / NUGGC / STK31 // SPN / LINC03124 / CLEC9A / MT1F / ITGBL1 / DLL1 / DUSP27 / RNU6-529P / FAM155A / TMEM240 / LINC00937 / LINC01907 / ZNF883.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic CTGF 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS CTGF									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T CTGF									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
PROM1 - CTGF	316	202	223	72	FMO1 - CTGF	315	140	246	386
IGF1 - CTGF	205	152	353	346	ELN - CTGF	208	141	214	365
SLC12A1 - CTGF	381	251	379	116	FBLN1 - CTGF	284	226	314	114
ADCYAP1R1 - CTGF	97	213	238	296	TRIM9 - CTGF	317	201	143	382
SRPX - CTGF	329	313	283	30	SLC17A7 - CTGF	354	309	272	305
AEBP1 - CTGF	227	93	241	385	BST1 - CTGF	150	230	219	352
ST8SIA1 - CTGF	290	271	355	66	NPR3 - CTGF	290	271	355	66
C1orf198 - CTGF	324	240	309	198	PHF19 - CTGF	327	267	330	289
PLXDC2 - CTGF	306	233	374	155	PDLIM2 - CTGF	271	389	239	252
CRISPLD1 - CTGF	365	278	311	203	CCR2 - CTGF	224	274	372	263
PHF24 - CTGF	239	375	249	45	PLAU - CTGF	209	228	306	120
BHLHE41 - CTGF	358	279	367	215	SLC12A5 - CTGF	133	335	319	300
TMEM35A - CTGF	263	312	267	254	FCHO1 - CTGF	364	327	263	143
PXDN - CTGF	252	325	204	279	LILRB2 - CTGF	318	297	285	242
C1QL1 - CTGF	308	318	287	35	SLC6A11 - CTGF	228	250	260	319
MYH10 - CTGF	348	350	356	221	CNTN6 - CTGF	238	257	209	343
PTPN22 - CTGF	323	290	388	277	FHOD3 - CTGF	216	303	257	48
FAIM2 - CTGF	102	264	274	323	LRCH1 - CTGF	355	333	362	210
LCPI - CTGF	258	292	229	261	ALPK3 - CTGF	386	269	332	247
ENPP2 - CTGF	338	342	370	159	IL11RA - CTGF	120	321	299	260
PLCB2 - CTGF	333	387	375	80	EMILIN1 - CTGF	292	392	381	192
FRAS1 - CTGF	236	289	248	67	CBLN3 - CTGF	265	277	392	208
FBLN5 - CTGF	299	295	328	62	MFGE8 - CTGF	107	246	220	350
IGFBP4 - CTGF	388	391	316	206	C1orf162 - CTGF	360	369	369	180
RBMS3 - CTGF	387	390	354	220	OSBPL10 - CTGF	325	300	346	269
FAM198A - CTGF	312	358	218	214	CTDSPL - CTGF	235	235	343	149
MYH15 - CTGF	264	221	340	345	FAM105A - CTGF	204	280	298	255
PIK3R1 - CTGF	218	244	271	309	SPATA9 - CTGF	283	238	258	367
LANCL3 - CTGF	274	344	278	122	CHST7 - CTGF	344	248	313	249
ADAM12 - CTGF	240	208	197	276	FEZ1 - CTGF	248	190	280	340
MKX - CTGF	322	210	232	383	ARID5B - CTGF	377	223	349	172
PRSS23 - CTGF	256	288	297	299	CRIM1 - CTGF	226	304	329	237
ENKUR - CTGF	353	328	385	178	ADAMTS12 - CTGF	68	247	230	389
KCNE4 - CTGF	378	349	277	82	DDAH1 - CTGF	372	314	339	193
ROBO3 - CTGF	361	379	207	272	C10orf90 - CTGF	221	218	228	290
MMP16 - CTGF	268	204	242	37	TSPAN7 - CTGF	280	376	119	354
SUSD3 - CTGF	137	388	261	207	MYO1E - CTGF	367	378	383	165

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between CTGF VS Individual members.

of CTGF-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS CTGF

RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T CTGF									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
SLAMF8 - CTGF	207	227	373	231	RUNX1 - CTGF	392	307	357	204
M1AP - CTGF	225	352	294	124	TCHH - CTGF	382	334	334	97
CHCHD6 - CTGF	247	383	342	144	SIGLEC11 - CTGF	349	380	371	227
SIGLEC16 - CTGF	166	310	327	270	LRP5 - CTGF	375	121	251	182
ELAVL4 - CTGF	253	347	217	288	MXRA8 - CTGF	383	305	310	161
NLRP3 - CTGF	200	320	326	110	CCDC74A - CTGF	335	222	290	94
NKX6-1 - CTGF	126	253	208	318	EBF1 - CTGF	118	282	307	366
TMEM200A - CTGF	345	385	348	156	COL1A2 - CTGF	320	357	390	258
HTRA1 - CTGF	210	261	235	241	MFAP4 - CTGF	55	234	288	378
TVP23A - CTGF	326	331	304	118	LDHD - CTGF	266	324	391	209
PRRT2 - CTGF	124	337	295	312	CYP2S1 - CTGF	346	362	244	148
NT5DC2 - CTGF	309	275	252	238	FILIP1L - CTGF	340	338	323	226
RAB31 - CTGF	385	361	222	243	NPNT - CTGF	343	315	268	197
ATOH8 - CTGF	289	384	344	160	VAMP5 - CTGF	213	263	292	284
ARMC4 - CTGF	108	272	266	330	CPT1C - CTGF	139	237	247	390
CCDC126 - CTGF	242	363	364	262	GPR183 - CTGF	366	330	273	177
ITGAM - CTGF	249	381	380	138	GPR27 - CTGF	251	192	256	280
MACROD2 - CTGF	368	245	368	200	IL17D - CTGF	155	284	270	292
SUSD5 - CTGF	373	283	166	351	HEG1 - CTGF	370	386	275	239
CD248 - CTGF	243	293	250	55	YPEL2 - CTGF	339	266	201	205
FAM131A - CTGF	211	345	352	100	MAMSTR - CTGF	140	353	359	282
FZD8 - CTGF	341	332	181	236	MYOZ1 - CTGF	229	193	212	336
PDE4DIP - CTGF	220	351	325	134	CSRNP3 - CTGF	350	258	366	250
CHTA - CTGF	331	296	389	257	KCNE1 - CTGF	276	360	382	125
NME9 - CTGF	233	354	358	95	PLAG1 - CTGF	314	370	302	141
EXT1 - CTGF	305	260	337	251	FAM43B - CTGF	330	329	200	21
ADRA2C - CTGF	279	254	296	301	CSF1 - CTGF	275	285	350	186
CYP4Z1 - CTGF	363	209	317	274	CYP4X1 - CTGF	384	355	335	130
RTN4RL2 - CTGF	352	326	360	166	C2orf88 - CTGF	310	343	377	266
KBTBD12 - CTGF	198	356	301	223	NUGGC - CTGF	357	232	183	357
STK31 - CTGF	362	287	320	170	SPN - CTGF	71	239	259	244
C2orf27A - CTGF	390	291	331	199	CLEC9A - CTGF	111	256	226	349
MT1F - CTGF	300	373	245	291	ITGBL1 - CTGF	337	249	324	218
DLL1 - CTGF	245	348	262	334	DUSP27 - CTGF	391	214	386	184
RNU6-529P - CTGF	293	374	173	232	FAM155A - CTGF	288	301	65	360
TMEM240 - CTGF	95	371	265	271	LINC00937 - CTGF	262	276	365	174
LINC01907 - CTGF	371	268	221	139	ZNF883 - CTGF	260	359	336	213

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between CTGF VS Individual members.

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t CTGF

PROM1 / FMO1 / IGF1 / ELN / SLC12A1 / FBLN1 ...
 ADCYAP1R1 / TRIM9 / SRPX / SLC17A7 / AEBP1 ...
 BST1 / ST8SIA1 / NPR3 / C1orf198 / PHF19 ...
 PLXDC2 / PDLIM2 / CRISPLD1 / CCR2 / PHF24 ...
 PLAU / BHLHE41 / SLC12A5 / TMEM35A / FCHO1 ...
 PXDN / LILRB2 / C1QL1 / SLC6A11 / MYH10 ...
 CNTN6 / PTPN22 / FHOD3 / FAIM2 / LRCH1 ...
 LCP1 / ALPK3 / ENPP2 / IL11RA / PLCB2 ...
 EMILIN1 / FRAS1 / CBLN3 / FBLN5 / MFGE8 ...
 IGFBP4 / C1orf162 / RBMS3 / OSBPL10 ...
 FAM198A / CTDSPL / MYH15 / FAM105A / PIK3R1 ...
 SPATA9 / LANCL3 / CHST7 / ADAM12 / FEZ1 ...
 MKX / ARID5B / PRSS23 / CRIM1 / ENKUR ...
 ADAMTS12 / KCNE4 / DDAH1 / ROBO3 / C10orf90 ...
 MMP16 / TSPAN7 / SUSD3 / MYO1E / SLAMF8 ...
 RUNX1 / M1AP / TCHH / CHCHD6 / SIGLEC11 ...
 SIGLEC16 / LRP5 / ELAVL4 / MXRA8 / NLRP3 ...
 CCDC74A / NKX6-1 / EBF1 / TMEM200A / COL1A2 ...
 HTRA1 / MFAP4 / TVP23A / LDHD / PRRT2 ...
 CYP2S1 / NT5DC2 / FILIP1L / RAB31 / NPNT ...
 ATOH8 / VAMP5 / ARMC4 / CPT1C / CCDC126 ...
 GPR183 / ITGAM / GPR27 / MACROD2 / IL17D ...
 SUSD5 / HEG1 / CD248 / YPEL2 / FAM131A ...
 MAMSTR / FZD8 / MYOZ1 / PDE4DIP / CSRNP3 ...
 CIITA / KCNE1 / NME1 / PLAG1 / EXT1 / FAM43B ...
 ADRA2C / CSF1 / CYP4Z1 / CYP4X1 / RTN4RL2 ...
 C2orf88 / KBTBD12 / NUGGC / STK31 / SPN ...
 LINC03124 / CLEC9A / MT1F / ITGBL1 / DLL1 ...
 DUSP27 / RNU6-529P / FAM155A / TMEM240 ...
 LINC00937 / LINC01907 / ZNF883 CTGF

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between CTGF and Individual members.

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